

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 129

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 129

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 129:0 A Song of Ascents.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 129:1</p>
<p>Psa. 129:1 “¹Many times they have ^{2a}persecuted me from my ^byouth up,” Let Israel now say, ²“¹Many times they have ²persecuted me from my youth up; Yet they have “not prevailed against me. ³“The plowers plowed upon my back; They lengthened their furrows.” ⁴The LORD “is righteous; He has cut in two the ^bcords of the wicked.</p>	<p>מִנְעוּרַי יֹאמְרוּ-נָא יִשְׂרָאֵל : ² רַבַּת צָרְרוּנִי מִנְעוּרַי גַּם לֹא-יִכְלוּ לִי : ³ עַל-גִּבִּי חָרְשׁוּ חֲרָשִׁים הֶאֱרִיכוּ לְמַעַנֹתָם [לְ] [מַעַנִּיתָם :] ⁴ יְהוָה צָדִיק קָצַץ עֲבוֹת רְשָׁעִים : ⁵ יִבְשׁוּ וַיִּסְגּוּ אַחֲזֹר כָּל שְׂנְאֵי צִיּוֹן : ⁶ יִהְיוּ כַחֲצִיר וַגָּזוֹת שֶׁקֶדְמָת שַׁלְיָהּ יִבֶּשׁ : ⁷ שֶׁלֹּא מִלֵּא כַפּוֹ קוֹצֵר וַחֲצָנוּ מִעֲמֹר : ⁸ וְלֹא אָמְרוּ הָעֹבְרִים בְּרַפְת־יְהוָה אֲלֵיכֶם בִּרְכָנוּ אֶתְכֶם בְּשֵׁם יְהוָה :</p>
<p>Psa. 129:5 May all who “hate Zion Be ^bput to shame and turned backward; ⁶ Let them be like “grass upon the housetops, Which withers before it ¹grows up; ⁷ With which the reaper does not fill his ¹hand, Or the binder of sheaves his ^abosom; ⁸ Nor do those who pass by say, “The ^ablessing of the LORD be upon you; We bless you in the name of the LORD.”</p>	

References

Psalm 129:1

¹Lit *Much*

²Lit *showed hostility toward*

^aEx 1:11; Judg 3:8; Ps 88:15

^bIs 47:12; Jer 2:2; 22:21; Ezek 16:22; Hos 2:15; 11:1

^cPs 124:1

Psalm 129:2

¹Lit *Much*

²Lit *showed hostility toward*

^aJer 1:19; 15:20; 20:11; Matt 16:18; 2 Cor 4:8, 9

Psalm 129:4

^aPs 119:137

^bPs 140:5

Psalm 129:5

^aMic 4:11

^bPs 70:3; 71:13

Psalm 129:6

¹Lit *draws out*

^a2 Kin 19:26; Ps 37:2; Is 37:27

Psalm 129:7

¹Lit *palm*

^aPs 79:12

Psalm 129:8

^aRuth 2:4; Ps 118:26

Targum

Psa. 129:1 A song that was uttered on the ascents of the abyss. Many are they who have oppressed me from my youth – let Israel now say – ² Many are they who have oppressed me from my youth, yet they have not been able to do me harm. ³ Upon my body the plowers have plowed, they have made their furrow long. ⁴ The LORD is righteous; he has severed the bonds of the wicked. ⁵ They will be ashamed and withdraw: all those who hate Zion. ⁶ They will be like the grass of the rooftops, which, before it blossoms, the east wind comes blowing on it and it has withered. ⁷ Which the reaper does not fill his hand with, nor the sheaver his shoulder. ⁸ And those who pass by do not say there, “The blessing of the LORD be upon you,” nor will they answer, “We bless you in the name of the LORD.”

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

The Psalmist encourages the reader to learn the annals of Jewish history. The diverse periods of history must not be viewed as separate occurrences but as one long lifetime. Every event in Israel's history is connected to some other event. It is also important to remember the painful times as well as the good times.

Notes on the Psalm

History repeats itself. The mistakes of the past are made over and over. The mistakes of the past need to be remembered so that they do not happen again. Covenants with the LORD are celebrated annually to remind the people of promises made. For example, the Passover and Shavuot are celebrated every year. This is to remind the people of the past events and the covenant that the LORD made with Israel. People like the circular year of events. It offers stability in an unstable world. People know when Nissan 1 comes that in fourteen days the Passover is celebrated. This gives people a side purpose of preparing for the celebration. The Passover celebration is a joyous time of the year because it commemorates Israel's freedom from the slavery of Egypt. Shavuot reminds the people of the day Moses received the Ten Commandments from the LORD. It is those events which bind the people to each other and to the LORD.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

